
Organizational Time Pressure and Safety: Exploring the role of Supportive and Safety Climates through a Cross-Level Moderated Mediation Model.

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RUNNING HEAD: Time pressure, support and safety climates.

Organizational Time Pressure and Safety: Exploring the role of Supportive and Safety
Climates through a Cross-Level Moderated Mediation Model.

Abstract

Purpose. Organizational time pressure can be regarded as a contextual factor influencing safety. However, research on the mechanisms that explain these negative cross-level effects and how to prevent them remains underexplored. This study addresses this research lacuna and provides insight into how the organizational context shapes employees' safety attitudes. With this purpose, this study expands the JD-R model to the organizational level and considers how different facets of climate interact with each other. This study tests whether the negative influence of organizational time pressure on employees' satisfaction with safety via the safety climate is weaker when the organizational support climate is high.

Methodology. Our sample comprised of 367 drivers from 33 Spanish road transport organizations. Structural equation modeling (SEM) was used to test the model.

Findings. The results supported the moderated mediation model, exhibiting a negative cross-level effect of organizational time pressure on satisfaction with safety, which was mediated by safety climate. Additionally, this indirect effect was conditional on the organizational support climate, which mitigated the negative influence of organizational time pressure on the safety climate and weakened the indirect effect when organizational support was high.

Originality. This study extends the JD-R model to the organizational level and examines how different facets of the organizational climate interact to influence safety.

Practical implications. These findings have significant practical implications for policies and practices aimed at mitigating the negative effects of organizational time pressure across different sectors.

Keywords: Organizational time pressure, organizational safety climate, organizational support climate, safety, professional driver.

Introduction

In modern organizations, time pressure has increased (Baethge *et al.*, 2018), especially in road transport, where unique time-related challenges arise (Pawar & Velaga, 2022; Petitta *et al.*, 2023). Time pressure becomes an organizational phenomenon (Bakker *et al.*, 2023) that affects safety (Useche *et al.*, 2017). However, research on its cross-level negative effects is limited. This study proposes a cross-level moderated mediation model to examine the mediating role of the organizational safety climate in the relationship between organizational time pressure and employee satisfaction with safety. It also tests whether organizational support climate moderates the time pressure-safety climate relationship.

This model contributes to understanding how organizational context shapes employees' safety attitudes by adopting a systemic approach to safety (Gamero *et al.*, 2018; Leveson *et al.*, 2009; Rasmussen, 1997). Organizational time pressure may shift safety norms about what is considered acceptable, normalizing deviance and weakening the safety climate (Rasmussen, 1997; Turner and Pidgeon, 1997). However, an organizational support climate can act as a counterforce, helping maintain safety boundaries (Rasmussen, 1997) by enabling alternative actions and interpretations. Thus, its buffering effect may mitigate the negative impact of time pressure on the safety climate.

This study contributes to climate research by addressing several gaps in the existing literature (Kuenzi and Schminke, 2009). Given that multiple climates coexist within organizations, understanding how they interact is crucial. This study examines how this interplay shapes the cross-level effect of organizational variables, such as organizational time pressure, on employee satisfaction with safety. Unlike prior research, which focused on facet climates and their direct correlates (e.g., safety climate

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3 and safety attitudes), this study highlights the role of broader climates, such as
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5 organizational support.
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8 Finally, this study extends JD-R model research to the organizational level
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10 (Guezzi *et al.*, 2020) framing organizational time pressure and support climate as
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12 collective job demands and resources. Moreover, it advances the understanding of the
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14 job resources that best meet specific job demands (Häusser *et al.*, 2010; Schaufeli and
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16 Taris, 2014).
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26 **Literature review and hypothesis development**

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28 *Organizational time pressure and satisfaction with safety*

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33 Time pressure results from a discrepancy between the tasks to be accomplished at
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35 work and the available working time (Briker *et al.*, 2021), and is regarded as a central
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37 occupational demand (Baethge *et al.*, 2018; Hoppe *et al.*, 2023). Most research has
38
39 conceptualized time pressure as an individual construct. Nonetheless, similar to other
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41 job demands, this can be seen as a characteristic inherent to organizational dynamics
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43 (Bakker *et al.*, 2023; Ghezzi *et al.*, 2020; Petitta *et al.*, 2023).
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48 Organizational time pressure reflects the perception of a lack of time to complete
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50 job-related tasks that are shared by all organizational members, and it emerges for
51
52 several reasons. Organizational members work under similar conditions (Bakker *et al.*,
53
54 2023; Ryan *et al.*, 1996). For instance, “*just in time*” management may result in tight
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56 deadlines, reinforcing shared perceptions of time pressure. Group dynamics, including
57
58 social information processes and sense-making, also play a role in shaping
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3 organizational time pressure. Organizational members interact with their peers, share
4 information, and interpret their work environments (Kozlowski and Klein, 2000).
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7 Organizational time pressure is expected to be negatively associated with employee
8 satisfaction with safety. It is a proxy for organizations' pressure toward cost-
9 effectiveness, which, according to the drift safety model (Rasmussen, 1997; 2000), may
10 lead to safety degradation. Employees may shift their focus from safety to productivity,
11 which may be perceived as most likely to be rewarded under time pressure (Clarke,
12 2012; Jiang and Probst, 2015; Sampson *et al.*, 2014). Consistently, Petitta *et al.* (2020)
13 showed that production pressure is a core organizational demand explaining employees'
14 health problems and subsequent work accidents and injuries.
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25 The cognitive-energetical theoretical framework (Hockey, 1997) suggests that
26 employees' cognitive and energetic capacity to attend safety may be reduced in highly
27 demanding work environments (Hockey and Earle, 2006; Turner *et al.*, 2010). Time
28 pressure limits the time for decision-making processes, affecting both information
29 processing and decision quality (Lin and Jia, 2023).
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37 Despite this, to our knowledge, no empirical evidence has explored the
38 relationship between organizational time pressure and individual satisfaction with
39 safety. Previous research has focused on the individual level of analyses and typically
40 used composite measures of job demands (e.g., hindrance demands) rather than the
41 single effect of particular job demands like time pressure. Some studies have shown that
42 occupational stress has the potential to result in individual failures, which lead to unsafe
43 acts or conditions and, consequently, accidents and injuries (Barkhordari *et al.*, 2019;
44 Leung *et al.*, 2016; Saleem *et al.*, 2022; Tong *et al.*, 2022). Seemingly, in the
45 transportation sector, several studies (Nguyen-Phuoc *et al.*, 2022; Useche *et al.*, 2017)
46 have found that occupational demands are detrimental to safety performance.
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3 However, the negative influence of composite measures of job demands
4 operationalized at the individual level cannot be extrapolated to the organizational level
5 or to specific job demands such as time pressure. Thus, this study extends previous
6 research by formulating the following hypothesis:
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12 *Hypothesis 1.* Organizational time pressure will be negatively associated with
13 employee satisfaction with safety.
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16 17 18 19 *The mediation role of organizational safety climate*

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21 Moreover, safety climate is expected to mediate the negative relationship
22 between organizational time pressure and employee satisfaction with safety. Safety
23 climate refers to employees' shared perception of their organization's policies,
24 procedures, and practices, as they relate to the value and importance of safety within the
25 organization (Griffin and Neal, 2000). It informs the relative priority of safety in
26 comparison to other competing goals in the organization (Zohar, 2014).
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35 Organizational time pressure might act as a competing operational demand that
36 is likely to negatively influence the safety climate (Zohar and Hofmann, 2012). When
37 organizational time pressure is high, safety policies and practices can be compromised
38 and the perception of the relative priority of safety may diminish. Organizational
39 complexity and competing goals make employees seek implicit signals about the
40 relative priority of safety through social exchanges among organizational members who
41 confront the same situations (Zohar and Hofmann, 2012). According to symbolic
42 interactionism and sense-making theories, this interpretative process allows for the
43 emergence of a safety climate (Schneider and Reichers, 1983). For instance, a post-
44 accident analysis of the Challenger space shuttle, in which a highly demanding
45 environment was in place, showed that changes in day-to-day processes to
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3 accommodate production pressures explained the weakening of the safety climate and
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5 drift into failure (Dekker *et al.*, 2011).
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8 However, the relationship between organizational time pressure and safety
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10 climate at the organizational level remains unexplored. Bunner *et al.* (2018) found that
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12 work intensification, that is, increased levels of quantitative workload in the previous
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14 two years, was negatively related to safety climate. Although this study does not focus
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16 specifically on organizational time pressure, it suggests its potential negative influence
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18 on the safety climate. However, further research is required to confirm this. Bunner *et*
19
20 *al.* (2018) inferred work intensification and safety climate from data provided by safety
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22 engineers and managers representing 122 high-risk organizations. Their expert
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24 evaluation was used as a proxy for work intensification and safety climate.
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29 At the individual level, Hansez and Chmiel (2010) found a non-significant
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31 relationship between job demands and perceived management commitment to safety, a
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33 key dimension of the safety climate. However, these authors suggest that using a
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35 composite measure of job demands may account for unexpected results and encourage
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37 future researchers to investigate the specific effects of different job demands such as
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39 organizational time pressure on safety correlates. This study responds to this research
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41 lacuna.
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46 Several theoretical arguments support the cross-level positive effect of safety
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48 climate on employee satisfaction with safety. The safety climate supports a specific
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50 organization's operational goal, which is safety; thus, it is likely to foster safety
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52 performance (Katz and Kahn, 1966; Kuenzi and Schminke, 2009) as well as satisfaction
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54 with safety. The theory of Planned Behavior (Ajzen, 1991) also supports the benefits of
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56 a safety climate. In a work environment in which significant others are perceived to be
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58 concerned with safety, the value of safety and its positive correlates are cultivated
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3 (Fogarty and Shaw, 2010). Consequently, individuals are expected to be more satisfied
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5 with safety.
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8 Moreover, empirical evidence has shown that an organizational safety climate
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10 increases employees' safety performance (Christian *et al.*, 2009; Guezzi *et al.*, 2020;
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12 Petitta *et al.*, 2017). In the transportation sector, the organizational safety climate
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14 diminished individuals' aberrant driving behavior in bus drivers from 30 companies in
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16 Taiwan (Chen *et al.*, 2019), and self-reported crash involvement in bus drivers of 13
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18 fleets in Shanghai (Wang *et al.*, 2021). These findings suggest that an organizational
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20 safety climate can enhance the safety satisfaction of professional drivers. This study
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22 contributes to the accumulation of knowledge on the cross-level effect of safety climate
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24 on safety correlates in a sample of professional Spanish drivers.
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28 Additionally, this study examines the mediating role of organizational safety
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30 climate. Organizational time pressure may weaken the organizational safety climate,
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32 reducing employee safety satisfaction. To our knowledge, this relationship remains
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34 unexplored.
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38 *Hypothesis 2.* Organizational safety climate will mediate the relationship
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40 between organizational time pressure and employees' satisfaction with safety.
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43 44 *The moderating role of organizational support climate*

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47 Given the potential impact of organizational time pressure on safety, it is
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49 important to explore ways to mitigate its negative effects. This study builds on previous
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51 research by examining the buffering role of organizational support climate.
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55 According to the JD-R model, job resources such as organizational support can
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57 buffer the negative effects of job demands on work outcomes. They shape how
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3 employees perceive demands and moderate responses following the appraisal process
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5 (Bakker *et al.*, 2023).
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8 The conservation of resources theory (COR) (Hobfoll, 1989) suggests that the
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10 negative effects of organizational time pressure may be attenuated when resources are
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12 available. An organizational support climate may serve as an environmental resource
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14 that helps employees to gain greater resources to cope with such pressure. Supportive
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16 organizations offer instrumental and socioemotional support (Sampson *et al.*, 2014),
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18 implement well-being policies (Hesketh and Cooper, 2023; Laine and Rinne, 2015;
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20 Pagán-Castaño *et al.*, 2020), and promote adherence to safety standards (Nguyen-Phuoc
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22 *et al.*, 2022; Tucker *et al.*, 2008). Thus, an organizational support climate may buffer
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24 the negative effects of organizational time pressure on the safety climate.
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28 According to the compensatory control model of effort regulation (Hockey,
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30 1997), in demanding organizational contexts, employees may prioritize high-value tasks
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32 at the expense of lower-priority ones. Without an organizational support climate,
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34 organizational time pressure may prompt a focus on work pace over safety, which is
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36 less visibly rewarded. In contrast, a supportive climate encourages employees to seek
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38 strategies and resources to manage competing demands without resorting to shortcuts.
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42 Additionally, when organizational support is high, resources such as adequate
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44 staffing and safety training are managed more effectively, enabling employees to cope
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46 with time pressure without compromising safety (Mearns and Reader, 2008). This
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48 becomes critical when time pressure depletes cognitive-energetic capacity to attend
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50 safety (Hansez and Chmiel, 2010). A supportive organizational climate is also
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52 characterized by open communication and frequent feedback (Duarte and Silva, 2023;
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54 Santiago, 2020) which facilitates the timely identification and resolution of safety
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56 issues, thereby reinforcing the safety climate even under pressure.
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3 Based on these arguments, the organizational support climate may serve as a key
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5 countervailing force (Rasmussen, 1997) that helps keep the system within safe
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7 boundaries. Despite theoretical support for its buffering role in the link between
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9 organizational time pressure and safety climate, this relationship remains unexplored.
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11 This study addresses this gap by testing Hypothesis 3:
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14 *Hypothesis 3.* Organizational support climate will moderate the relationship
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16 between organizational time pressure and organizational safety climate, such that the
17
18 negative association is stronger when the shared organizational support climate is low.
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21 Finally, this study addresses a gap in prior research by examining how multiple
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23 organizational goals and climates coexist and interact to shape employees' safety
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25 attitudes (Kuenzi and Schminke, 2009). While organizational time pressure may
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27 undermine the safety climate (Rasmussen, 1997; Turner and Pidgeon, 1997), a
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29 supportive climate can counteract its adverse effects (Rasmussen, 1997) and, in turn,
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31 reduce the negative indirect effect of organizational time pressure on safety satisfaction
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33 via the safety climate.
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37 Several theoretical perspectives support this moderated mediation hypothesis.
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39 According to the JD-R model, a supportive organizational climate buffers the
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41 detrimental effects of organizational time pressure on safety climate (Bakker et al.,
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43 2023). Furthermore, COR theory suggests that supportive climates provide instrumental
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45 and socioemotional resources (Hobfoll, 1989), enabling employees to develop strategies
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47 for dealing with competing demands, such as time pressure and safety (Hockey, 1997).
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49 Consequently, the detrimental effect of organizational time pressure on safety climate is
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51 reduced. Accordingly, the negative indirect effect of organizational time pressure on
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53 employees' safety satisfaction via safety climate is weaker under high levels of
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55 organizational support climate.
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3 *Hypothesis 4.* Organizational time pressure will influence employees'
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5 satisfaction with safety through its indirect effect via organizational safety climate, and
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7 the indirect effect will be weaker when the organizational support climate is high.
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10 **Method**

11 *Sample and procedure*

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16 The sample consisted of 33 Spanish road transport organizations of 107 companies
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18 contacted to participate in this study (response rate of 31.8%). Most organizations were
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20 small (less than 25 employees) (41.4%) or medium (less than 250 employees) (44.8%).
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22 Only 13.8% of the respondents were large (more than 250 employees). Fifty-nine
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24 percent of the organizations were dedicated to the transportation of goods, and 41% to
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26 passenger transportation.
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31 A survey was administered to 367 drivers. In most cases, questionnaires were
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33 collected through group sessions during working time. In every group session, the
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35 researchers explained the purpose of the research project and assured confidentiality.
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37 Nonetheless, in some organizations, surveys were sent by post, together with stamped
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39 envelopes. The survey was accompanied by an instruction letter detailing the purpose of
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41 the research project and the contact information. Eighty-seven percent of the
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43 participants were male. Sixty percent were between 35 and 55 years of age, 30% were
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45 less than 35 years of age, and 10% were 55 years of age or older. Regarding academic
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47 level, 16.3% had no academic title, 51.7% had completed primary education, 30.5% had
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49 secondary education, and 1.5% were university graduates. Most drivers had previous
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51 experience in the road sector (56.5%).
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56 *Measures*

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Organizational time pressure. The drivers' shared perceptions of time pressure were measured using three items adapted from Semmer *et al.* (1995; 1999). Drivers answered using a 5-point scale ("1. *Never*", "5. *Always*"). An example item is "Regarding your recent work, how often do you feel pressured due to the lack of time?". The Cronbach's alpha coefficient was .87. Individual scores were aggregated at the organizational level using a direct consensus model (Chan, 1998). Before aggregating, we assessed the within-team agreement using the Average Deviation Index ($AD_{M(j)}$) proposed by Burke *et al.* (1999). Burke and Dunlap (2002) recommend using the criterion $AD_{M(j)} \leq c/6$, where c is the number of response alternatives to interpret the index. For a Likert-type 5-point scale, $c/6 = .83$. Consequently, we concluded that there was within-team agreement when the $AD_{M(j)}$ values were equal to or less than .83. The average $AD_{M(j)}$ value was .63 ($SD = .24$). Thus, using the criterion equal to .83 from Burke and Dunlap (2002) for interpreting AD values, we concluded that the level of within-team agreement was sufficient to aggregate individual scores to the organizational level. We also assessed whether there were sufficient differences in the level of time pressure among different organizations using a one-way ANOVAs. The observed F value was significant ($F_{(32, 366)} = 2.69, p < .01$).

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Organizational safety climate. Drivers' perceptions of the safety climate in the organization were measured using three items adapted from existing questionnaires (Cox and Cheyne, 2000; Mearns *et al.*, 2003). A 5-point rating scale was used for the items, with responses ranging from 1 (*Strongly disagree*) to 5 (*Strongly agree*). Sample items include "In this company, safety is the first priority". Drivers' scores were aggregated at the organizational level following a referent-shift consensus model (Chan, 1998). The average $AD_{M(j)}$ value was .65 ($SD = .33$). Thus, we concluded that drivers' scores on this scale could be aggregated at the organizational level. The one-way

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3 ANOVA result was also significant ($F_{(32,366)} = 3.05, p < .01$), presenting significant
4 differences among organizations. Thus, we may consider that there is sufficient
5 evidence to support the validity of the aggregated measure. The Cronbach's alpha
6 coefficient was .82.
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13 *The organizational support climate* was measured using three items from González-
14 Romá *et al.*'s (2009) scale. Given that the scale was designed to measure team climate,
15 we adapted the referent to the organizational level (e.g., "*In my company, individuals*
16 *feel supported by the organization*"). Respondents answered using a 6-point scale (1=
17 *Strongly disagree*, 6=*Strongly agree*). The Cronbach's alpha was .95. The support
18 climate was operationalized by aggregating drivers' scores following a referent-shift
19 consensus model of composition (Chan, 1998). For a Likert-type 6-point scale, $c/6$ is
20 equal to 1. The average *AD* value was .63 ($SD=.26$). Thus, we concluded that the level
21 of agreement was sufficient to aggregate individual scores at the organizational level.
22 We also assessed whether there were sufficient differences in support climate among
23 organizations using a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA). The observed *F* value
24 was $F_{(32, 366)} = 5.43, p < .01$. This result showed adequate between-organizations
25 discrimination in support climate, and supported the validity of the aggregated measure
26 (Chan, 1998).
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47 **The convergent and discriminant validity of the organizational variables**
48 **(organizational time pressure, safety climate, and support climate) were tested as**
49 **follows. Following Hair et al. (2009), convergent validity was assessed using three**
50 **criteria: standardized factor loadings greater than .50, composite reliability (CR) values**
51 **above .70, and average variance extracted (AVE) values exceeding .50. All three**
52 **constructs exceeded these thresholds, providing strong evidence of convergent validity**
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(see Table I). Discriminant validity was also evaluated using Fornell and Larcker's (1981) criterion, which states that the square root of each construct's AVE should exceed its correlations with other constructs. Table II presents the correlation matrix. These exceeded the inter-construct correlations, confirming discriminant validity.

--- Insert Table I here ---

--- Insert Table II here ---

Satisfaction with safety was measured using the item "I am satisfied with safety at work" developed by González-Romá and Peiró (2004). Drivers responded to the item using a 5-point scale (from 1 = *Almost never* to 5 = *Almost always*).

Control variables. *Organizational size* was a control variable in our study to reduce the probability of attributing phenomena related to organizational size to the effects of shared perceptions of time pressure, and support and safety climates. Organizational size has been associated with employees' levels of satisfaction with safety (Probst and Estrada, 2010).

Data analysis

Our dataset comprised data at the organizational level (Level 2: organizational size, organizational time pressure, and organizational support and safety climates) and the individual level (Level 1: individual satisfaction with safety). Multilevel structural equation modeling (SEM) was conducted using *Mplus* Version 8 (Muthén and Muthén, 2017) to test our hypotheses.

Results

Table III presents means, standard deviations, and bivariate zero-order correlations. Both organizational- and individual-level correlations provided preliminary support for the hypothesized relationships. Correlations were statistically significant and aligned with the expected direction.

--- Insert Table III here ---

To test our hypotheses, we tested three relationship models. Model 1 tested the cross-level main effect of organizational time pressure on employees' satisfaction with safety. Model 2 tested the mediation effect of organizational safety climate on the cross-level relationship between organizational time pressure and individual satisfaction with safety. Model 3 tested the cross-level moderated mediation model, where organizational support climate was introduced as the moderator of the relationship between organizational time pressure and safety climate. The statistic TRd was calculated to compare these three models. TRd statistic is distributed chi-square comparing the log-likelihoods for the null and alternative models, with $df = p_1 - p_0$. When Model 2 and Model 1 were compared, the increase of log-likelihood (DLog-likelihood=10.43) was significant ($\chi^2_{(5)} = 20.06, p < .01$). When Model 3 and Model 2 were compared, the increase of log-likelihood (DLog-likelihood=31.83) was significant ($\chi^2_{(5)} = 707.33, p < .01$). Table IV displays these results.

Model 1 showed a significant negative association between organizational time pressure and satisfaction with safety ($\gamma = -.45, p < .01$), supporting Hypothesis 1. Moreover, organizational safety climate was positively related to satisfaction with safety ($\gamma = .74, p < .01$) (see Model 2). Organizational safety climate also significantly mediated the relationship between organizational time pressure and individual

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3 satisfaction with safety (indirect effect = $-.33$, 95% bias-corrected bootstrap CI [$-.636$, -
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5 $.025$]. These findings supported Hypothesis 2.
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9 Organizational support climate moderated the effect of organizational time pressure
10 on organizational safety climate ($\gamma = .20$, $p < .01$). Therefore, Hypothesis 3 was
11 supported. To better understand this interaction effect, we plotted it following the
12 procedure outlined by Aiken and West (1991). Figure 2 presents the plot of the
13 interaction between organizational time pressure and organizational support climate.
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15 The simple slopes analysis indicated that the slopes were significant for high levels ($t =$
16 7.27 , $p < .01$) and low levels ($t = 14.86$, $p < .01$) of organizational support climate.
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18 Thus, a high level of organizational support climate buffered the negative relationship
19 between organizational time pressure and safety climate. When the level of
20 organizational support climate was low, a high level of organizational time pressure was
21 associated with a low level of safety climate. However, when the level of organizational
22 support climate was high, the negative impact of high organizational time pressure on
23 safety climate was lower.
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39 To test Hypothesis 4, which proposed that the indirect effect of organizational time
40 pressure on individual satisfaction with safety through organizational safety climate is
41 conditional on organizational support climate, we conducted a multilevel moderated
42 mediation model. The Index of Moderated Mediation testing the hypothesized
43 conditional indirect effect was statistically significant ($B = .132$, $SE = .055$, 95% CI =
44 $.046$, $.258$). **Table V** shows confidence intervals (CIs) for bootstrap tests at three
45 organizational support climate values: (1) one standard deviation (SD) below the mean,
46 (2) mean, and (3) one SD above the mean. Results indicated that the conditional indirect
47 effect of organizational time pressure on satisfaction with safety was consistently
48 negative and became weaker as the organizational support climate increased, becoming
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3 not significant under conditions of high organizational support climate. These results
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5 supported Hypothesis 4.
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18 19 Discussion

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21 This study tested the cross-level effect of organizational time pressure on
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23 employees' safety satisfaction via safety climate. Additionally, it examined the
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25 moderating role of organizational support climate in the relationship between
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27 organizational time pressure and safety climate.
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31 The results revealed that organizational time pressure was negatively associated
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33 with individuals' safety satisfaction, consistent with previous research linking job
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35 demands with reduced safety performance at the individual level of analysis (Nguyen-
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37 Phuoc *et al.*, 2022; Useche *et al.*, 2017). Moreover, it extends previous research by
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39 adopting a multilevel perspective that acknowledges the relevance of the organizational
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41 context. Evidence has shown that organizational time pressure is a relevant job demand
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43 and discourages future research from considering it as part of a composite measure of
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45 job demands (e.g., hindrance demands).
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50 Organizational safety climate mediated the negative influence of organizational
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52 time pressure on employees' satisfaction with safety. Organizational time pressure was
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54 negatively associated with organizational safety climate, which is consistent with the
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56 negative relationship established between work intensification and safety climate
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58 (Bunner *et al.*, 2018) at the organizational level. The cross-level effect of organizational
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3 safety climate on employees' safety satisfaction is consistent with previous research
4 supporting the benefits of a safety climate for safety (Chen *et al.*, 2019; Christian *et al.*,
5 2009; Ghezzi *et al.*, 2020; Petitta *et al.*, 2017).
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11 Furthermore, the findings showed that an organizational support climate buffers
12 the negative relationship between organizational time pressure and safety climate. As
13 expected, the conditional indirect effect became weaker as support climate increased.
14 These findings are in line with Clarke's (2012) meta-analysis, which concluded that
15 third variables might moderate the association between occupational stress and safety.
16 Consistent with the JD-R buffer hypothesis (Bakker and Demerouti, 2007; Bakker *et al.*,
17 2023), resources, such as support, can mitigate the negative impact of job demands on
18 safety.
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30 *Theoretical implications*

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32 This study has several theoretical implications. The findings support the
33 relevance of the Job Demands-Resources (JDR) model (Bakker and Demerouti, 2007)
34 in understanding safety issues, which is consistent with previous research (e.g., Li *et al.*,
35 2013; Nahrgang *et al.*, 2011; Snyder *et al.*, 2008). The findings also emphasize the
36 importance of examining specific job demands and matching resources (Häusser *et al.*,
37 2010; Schaufeli and Taris, 2014). The results indicated that time pressure is a key
38 predictor of safety climate, and that organizational support climate helps to mitigate its
39 negative effects.
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52 This study has important implications for multilevel research into organizational
53 climate, stress, and safety. Kuenzi and Schminke (2009) called for a holistic approach to
54 climate research, recognizing that climate facets interact in complex ways to influence
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3 outcomes like safety (Schneider *et al.*, 2016; West and Lyubovnikova, 2015). This
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5 study responds to this call and advances the climate research.
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8 Regarding stress research, this study suggests that job demands and resources go
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10 beyond employees' subjective interpretations, encouraging further multilevel research
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12 on JD-R model (Bakker and Demerouti, 2007). Considering them as shared
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14 organizational characteristics is essential (Bakker *et al.*, 2023). Stress among
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16 professional drivers has generally been addressed at the individual level (e.g., Dorn,
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18 2005; Legree *et al.*, 2003; Meng *et al.*, 2016; Rahimpour *et al.*, 2020; Useche *et al.*,
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20 2017), rather than as a collective phenomenon. However, multilevel research on the JD-
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22 R theory has emerged as a promising area in the last decade, although empirical
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24 evidence remains limited (Bakker *et al.*, 2023).
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28 This study adopts a systemic approach that shows how social and organizational
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30 factors interact to shape safety in organizations (Leveson, 2017; Rasmussen, 1997).
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32 Evidence suggests that organizations providing both instrumental and socioemotional
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34 support help employees cope with job demands (Jolly *et al.*, 2021). However, support as
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36 a moderating resource in mitigating the impact of job demands on safety had not been
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38 explored.
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42 Finally, this approach shifts the focus of safety prediction from individual to
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44 organizational and social factors. Traditionally, research has emphasized individual
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46 factors, like driving behaviors, while neglecting organizational influences and system
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48 safety principles (Dallat *et al.*, 2019). Our findings support a more comprehensive
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50 approach that is consistent with recent safety theories. Overall, our results highlight the
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52 importance of incorporating the organizational level of analysis into both stress
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54 (Schaufeli and Taris, 2014; Bakker *et al.*, 2023) and safety research (e.g., Hofmann *et*
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56 *al.*, 2017; Zohar and Luria, 2005).
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Practical implications

These findings provide valuable insights for organizations seeking to improve their employees' safety attitudes, particularly in demanding environments. To mitigate the negative effects of organizational time pressure, interventions should involve adjusting workloads, setting more realistic deadlines (e.g., incorporating employee input during planning phases) and allocating resources more effectively (e.g., by increasing staffing during peak periods or automating repetitive tasks). Providing time management training and clarifying task priorities can also help employees to cope with time demands more effectively.

Importantly, the study also reveals that a supportive organizational climate can buffer the negative impact of time pressure on safety. Practical measures may include developing supportive leadership, fostering team cohesion and offering accessible resources, such as mentoring or peer support, and internal communication channels to express employees' concerns.

These implications extend to contexts marked by economic constraints and lean staffing. Managing organizational time pressure and strengthening a supportive climate can help to balance competing organizational goals (e.g., that is safety and productivity).

Limitations and future research directions

This study has several limitations. First, the cross-sectional design restricts the ability to draw causal inferences. The relationship between the organizational support climate and safety climate may be reciprocal (Dollard and Bakker, 2010). Second, the study lacks objective safety indicators, as transportation organizations often withhold accident data, particularly that relating to non-fatal incidents. Future research should incorporate objective indicators to detect early signs of safety system degradation.

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3 Future research could explore various job demands and mechanisms to mitigate
4 their negative effects. Depending on the job demands, different job resources may
5 become more prominent. This study also encourages applying JD-R model to better
6 understand safety, as it offers insights into managing organizational trade-offs like time
7 pressure and safety. Additionally, future research should examine the interrelationships
8 between facet-specific climates and their influence on individuals' attitudes and
9 behaviors.
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19 *Conclusions*

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21 This multilevel study highlights the critical role of organizational context in
22 shaping safety attitudes. Understanding the interplay between different facets of
23 organizational climate sheds light on the mechanisms explaining the negative influence
24 of organizational time pressure on employee satisfaction with safety. The findings
25 showed that organizational time pressure negatively influences the safety climate, which
26 in turn influences employee satisfaction with safety. Notably, a supportive
27 organizational climate can act as a buffer to mitigate the detrimental effects of time
28 pressure on the safety climate. Thus, the effect of organizational time pressure on
29 satisfaction with safety via safety climate depends on the level of organizational support
30 climate, becoming weaker under conditions of high support.
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Table I. Convergent Validity Indicators for Latent Constructs

Construct	Standardized Loadings	CR	AVE
Organizational time pressure	0.82, 0.90, 0.79	0.877	0.704
Organizational safety climate	0.84, 0.91, 0.64	0.844	0.648
Organizational support climate	0.82, 0.85, 0.82	0.869	0.689

Note. All factor loadings were statistically significant ($p < .001$).

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Table II. Discriminant Validity: Correlation Matrix and AVE Square Roots

Construct	1	2	3
1. Organizational time pressure	0.84		
2. Organizational safety climate	-0.44	0.80	
3. Organizational support climate	-0.34	0.47	0.83

Note. AVE square roots on the diagonal

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Table III. Descriptive Statistics and Correlations for the Study Variables.

	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	1	2	3	4	5
1. Organizational size	6.16	2.45	-	-	-	-	-
2. Organizational time pressure	2.69	.47	.04	-	-.33**	-.40**	-.34**
3. Organizational safety climate	3.65	.39	-.27**	-.56**	-	.55**	.63**
4. Organizational support climate	3.22	.61	-.66**	-.45**	.56**	-	.56**
5. Satisfaction with safety	3.79	.93	-	-	-	-	-

Note. Correlations below the diagonal are organizational-level correlations ($N = 33$). Correlations above the diagonal are individual-level correlations ($N = 367$). * $p < .05$; ** $p < .01$; one-tailed.

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Table IV. Multilevel Estimates for Models.

	Model 1		Model 2				Model 3			
	Predictors		Simple mediation				Moderated mediation			
	Satisfaction with safety		Organizational safety climate		Satisfaction with safety		Organizational safety climate		Satisfaction with safety	
	Estimate	SE	Estimate	SE	Estimate	SE	Estimate	SE	Estimate	SE
Intercept	5.383**	.281	5.079**	.537	1.523	1.033	4.203**	.439	1.893**	.730
Organizational size	-.061	.047	-.036	.033	-.033*	.019	.031	.048	-.046*	.021
Organizational time pressure	-.448**	.097	-.445**	.172	-.088	.121	-.890**	.193	-.112	.109
Organizational safety climate					.742**	.174			.708**	.132
Interaction: Organizational time pressure*Organizational support climate							.197**	.068		
Log-likelihood	-686.85		-697.28				-729.11			
Δ Log-likelihood			10.43**				31.83**			
Scaling correction factor	1.88		1.05				0.75			
Parameters	9		14				19			

Note. * $p < .05$; ** $p < .01$; one-tailed

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Table V. Results for the conditional indirect effects

Conditional Indirect Effect (95%)				
Support climate	Effect	<i>BootSE</i>	<i>BootLLCI</i>	<i>BootULCI</i>
Low (-1SD)	-.246	.096	-.431	-.104
Medium	-.165	.098	-.332	-.017
High (+1SD)	-.086	.112	-.278	.085

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Figure 1. The moderated mediation model

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Figure 2. The moderating role of organizational support climate in the relationship between organizational time pressure and safety climate

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